

HEALTH AND MEDICINE

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Annotatsiya: Dive into the field of health and medicine, a subject that encompasses the study of the prevention, cure, and understanding of disease as well as the investigation of physical and mental well-being. This topic includes health care, medicine, human anatomy, and patient’s access to care. To improve a patient’s health, medical professionals use therapy, medications, and diets

Keywords: medicine, common, clinical, responsibilities, represents, cure, human, health,diets,therapy

Аннотация: Погрузитесь в область здравоохранения и медицины, предмет, который включает в себя изучение профилактики, лечения и понимания болезней, а также исследование физического и психического благополучия. Эта тема включает здравоохранение, медицину, анатомию человека и доступ пациентов к медицинской помощи. Для улучшения здоровья пациента медицинские работники используют терапию, медикаменты и диеты.

Ключевые слова: медицина, общая, клиническая, обязанности, представляет, лечение, человек, здоровье, диеты, терапия.

INTRODUCTION.

Medicine and Health encompasses the study of the prevention, cure, and understanding of disease as well as the investigation of physical and mental wellbeing. Oxford Reference provides more than 82,000 concise definitions and in-depth, specialist encyclopedic entries on the wide range of subjects within this discipline.

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Written by trusted experts for researchers at every level, our coverage comprises authoritative, highly accessible information on the very latest terminology, theories, treatments, people, and organizations relating to all areas of medicine and health—from public health, psychology, sports science, and food and nutrition, to biomedicine, epidemiology, nursing, and plastic surgery.

Medicine has been practiced since prehistoric times, and for most of this time it was an art (an area of creativity and skill), frequently having connections to the religious and philosophical beliefs of local culture. For example, a medicine man would apply herbs and say prayers for healing, or an ancient philosopher and physician would apply bloodletting according to the theories of humorism. In recent centuries, since the advent of modern science, most medicine has become a combination of art and science (both basic and applied, under the umbrella of medical science). For example, while stitching technique for sutures is an art learned through practice, knowledge of what happens at the cellular and molecular level in the tissues being stitched arises through science.

Prescientific forms of medicine, now known as traditional medicine or folk medicine, remain commonly used in the absence of scientific medicine and are thus called alternative medicine. Alternative treatments outside of scientific medicine with ethical, safety and efficacy concerns are termed quackery.

THE MAIN PART.

Medicine is — the science[1] and practice[2] of — caring — for a patient, managing the diagnosis, prognosis, prevention, treatment, palliation of their injury or disease, and promoting their health. Medicine encompasses a variety of health care practices evolved to maintain and restore health by the prevention and treatment of illness. Contemporary medicine applies biomedical sciences, biomedical research, genetics, and medical technology to diagnose, treat, and prevent injury and disease, typically through pharmaceuticals or surgery, but also through therapies as diverse as psychotherapy, external splints and traction, medical devices, biologics, and ionizing radiation, amongst others.[3]

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Health: Health is the state of mental, social and physical well-being and not just being disease-free.

Physical health:

Emotional health:

Social health:

Spiritual health: Spiritual health includes values that help us to live a purposeful life.

Intellectual health:

Mental and physical health are probably the two most frequently discussed types of health.

Spiritual, emotional, and financial health also contribute to overall health. Medical experts have linked these to lower stress levels and improved mental and physical well-being.

CONCLUSION.

People with better financial health, for example, may worry less about finances and have the means to buy fresh food more regularly. Those with good spiritual health may feel a sense of calm and purpose that fuels good mental health.

Clinical medicine is a very common form of medicine, where it represents the general clinician's responsibilities toward patients. The ways of treatment and understanding of patients' problems are very important to understand the disease and create health plans. Thus, clinical medicine has an important role in the diagnosis process. Clinical medicine deals with body basics and human anatomy; relating problems in human parts are the major concept. Patients with any basic issues visit their primary health clinic for clinical medicine and make follow-up appointments with their primary care doctor. The preliminary concept of clinical medicine is having a vital role in general health research. General diagnosis is very important in clinical medicine, which primarily includes examining the patient.

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